

A SCHEME OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN ABU DHABI GOVERNMENT ENTITIES

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to determine the determinants of knowledge management strategies towards organizational performance in Abu Dhabi government entities. After proposing a testable conceptual framework, this study initiated to propose the research framework by an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), where the items of the further research can have some light to move forward. The sample size was 331 for this study and simple random sampling was employed. For this research, the findings show that, Knowledge Management Structure, Knowledge Management Practice, Knowledge and Management Strategy are the important aspects of Organizational Performance in Abu Dhabi government entities. This research has contributed to the existing knowledge by proposing an empirically validated research model which could be an important execution tool for the success of government entities performance.

Keywords: knowledge management, organizational performance, government entities, Abu Dhabi

1. Introduction

Knowledge management is considered as the essential tool to bring reforms by governments for the societal improvements and implementing strategies (Azam &

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Moha Asri; 2015; Tarofder et al., 2017). However, it has been repeatedly noted that the government policy initiatives for the reform of public organization have largely failed to promote knowledge creation. Moreover, the knowledge management in private sector has been adopted earlier in comparison to the public sector where the governments have been found struggling to implement the notion of knowledge management due to intrinsic barriers associated with organizational knowledge. The implementation of the knowledge based system into public sector organizations for the knowledge capture and knowledge sharing components of the knowledge management processes are very important. It is very important for the knowledge capture and knowledge sharing components of the knowledge management processes are very important. The management and the organizational knowledge have to be integrated into the process and procedures of the organization for increased growth and performance. It is very important for the knowledge capture and knowledge sharing components of the knowledge management processes are very important. The management and the organizational knowledge have to be integrated into the process and procedures of the organization for increased growth and performance (Liebenskind 1996). In order to pave the way for the knowledge management in any organization, the organizational management must improve the organizational culture to enhance adaptability among the staff (Zander & Kogut, 1995).

Nevertheless, absence of a comprehensive knowledge in this regards hinders the effort of the organizational performance in Abu Dhabi government entities. Thus, it is important to examine whether there is a significant relationship between the knowledge management strategies and organizational performance in Abu Dhabi. Furthermore, the research questions designed for this quantitative study also aim to determine the correlation between the knowledge management strategies and the organizational performance while identifying the factors affecting knowledge management in the context of Abu Dhabi.

2. Literature Review

The management and the organizational knowledge have to be integrated into the process and procedures of the organization for increased growth and performance (Dahari et al., 2011; Azam et al., 2014; Tham et al., 2017). It is very important for the knowledge capture and knowledge sharing components of the knowledge management processes are very important (Tsoukas, 2005). However, there is no uniformity or common conformity on the part of the scholars as to the definition and nature of knowledge, an intrinsically ambiguous or equivocal term.

Since the time of the ancient Greek philosophers, Western thought has been dominated by the study of epistemology, or the nature, sources, limitations and validity of knowledge (Sankaran, 2006). In 360 BC, in his *Theaetetus*, Plato defines knowledge as 'justified true belief' (Project Gutenberg, 1999). Although debated and modified in many ways, Plato's concept of knowledge is still widely articulated in Western thought (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). More recently, Drucker (1993) coins the term 'knowledge worker' and argued that, in the 'knowledge society', it was no longer capital or labor or natural resources, rather the knowledge that would be the basic economic resource.

Knowledge management is managing the corporation's knowledge through a systematically and organizationally specified process for acquiring, organizing, sustaining, applying, sharing and renewing both the tacit and explicit knowledge of employees to enhance organizational performance and create value (Allee, 1997; Davenport *et al.*, 1998; Alavi and Leidner, 2001). This caters to the critical issues of organisational adaptation, survival and competence in face of increasingly discontinuous environmental change; it embodies organizational processes that seek synergistic combination of data and information processing capacity of information technologies and the innovative capacity of human beings (Malhotra, 1998). Gupta *et al.* (2000) mentioned that, knowledge management is a process that helps organizations find, select, organize, disseminate, and transfer important information and expertise necessary for activities. Other researcher (Bhatt, 2001; Holm, 2001; Horwitch and Armacost, 2002) defined that, knowledge management is the creation, extraction, transformation and storage of the correct knowledge and information in order to design better policy, modify action and deliver results.

According to Allee (1997), knowledge is experience that can be communicated and shared; though, by experience, he emphasizes more on information. This is echoed by Leonard and Sensiper (1998), who believe such information is tacit in nature. Bhagat *et al.* (2002) embrace the notion that knowledge is derived from creation and restructuring of information, which, according to Beckman (1997), enhances an individual's productivity, problem-solving and decision-making skills through logical reasoning.

While defining the knowledge, Cavaleri and Reed (2000) mention that knowledge, essentially, is composed of and grounded in potential acts/activities or signs – social in nature. These can be relevant to political issues and beliefs resulting from an individual's experience. This knowledge denotes the capacity for effective action. Davenport and Prusak (1998, p.5) hold that knowledge is the '*fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information, and expert insight originated in the minds of the*

knowers. In an organization, it often becomes embedded not only in documents or repositories but also in organizational routines, processes, strategies, and norms.'

In these times of intense competition, firms are striving to cope with the challenges posed by various forces ranging from globalization to the diffusion of technology innovation to the creation, adoption and dissemination of knowledge (Haque et al., 2014; Moha Asri & Azam, 2015; Haur et al., 2017). The upshot of such tumultuous changes has caused a paradigm shift in setting firm priorities that lay emphasis more on the utilization of its knowledge base than on the physical resources at its disposal. Consequently, conventional business strategies must adjust to the dynamics of the evolving business landscape through the employment of knowledge-based resources in order to harvest a sustained competitive advantage (Grover and Davenport, 2001; Jackson *et al.* 2003; Sharkie, 2003). Firms, which are involved in such generation and deployment of knowledge, are, therefore, poised to reap the windfalls in these days of exponential knowledge growth. It is thus no wonder that various aspects concerning knowledge management have consumed a considerable attention from academicians as well as industry players with the latter beginning to envisage managing their knowledge-base as part of their overall strategic initiatives (Hung *et al.*, 2005).

3. Research Methodology

Research design consists of three main types namely descriptive, explorative and experimental. The current study is using the descriptive design as the most appropriate study design for this kind of study. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), "*descriptive study is under taken in order to ascertain and be able to describe the characteristics of the variables of interest in a situation*" (p.105). This type of study is a guide for making observations to proper documentation of phenomenon of interest based on scientific method and therefore it is more reliable than doing casual observation which is conducted by untrained people (Bhattacharjee, 2012).

The main purpose of the study is to determine the knowledge management strategies and organizational performance in Abu Dhabi Government Entities. The sample size was 331 for this study and simple random sampling was employed. Besides, the two main methods which consist in research approach are deductive and inductive (quantitative and qualitative approach). Quantitative method relies on the collection of quantitative data which is mainly used in descriptive studies for testing a theory. So, to test the specific relationship of hypotheses, quantitative data must be collected to analyze the relationship and finally the result could be generalized on the

population and select a sufficient sample size which represents the whole population. For this research, the data are subsequently analyzed to explain the relationships among the variables by employing statistical analysis namely descriptive and inferential statistics.

4. Research Findings

The composition of the sample indicated that the 88% of respondents are represented by males while the remaining 12% are represented by the female respondents. Findings reveal that the largest group of respondents fell into the 31-35 years age group (41%), followed closely by 41% are above the 36 year age group. Of the rest closely by the 26 - 30 age groups at 15% and below 20 year age group represent by 9%. The educational level of the respondents reflects that the most of the executive officers that had a degree which is noted at 42.5%, 10.0% had a diploma while 30% had the secondary education qualification and 16.9% of the respondents' had qualified with school training. In order to that most of the non-executives of government entities who, are qualified with a degree which is evident from the study.

Item-wise descriptive statistics are presented in Table 1 below. From the table, it can be observed that the item *"In their government work, our employees rely on experience, skills and knowledge"* has achieved the highest mean value (4.480) with a standard deviation of .670. This confirms that majority of the respondents strongly agreed that government work activities are emphasized by employees' experience, skills and knowledge. On the other hand, the item *"Managerial records are kept in proper manner in our organization"* has achieved the lowest mean score of 3.480 with a standard deviation of .932. This means that majority of the respondents neither agree nor disagree to this statement.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Code	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation
Q1	Our employees obtain a good extent of new knowledge from internal and external sources	4.22	.763
Q2	Our employees gain new knowledge from business partners and rivals	4.42	.651
Q3	Our organization recognizes knowledge creation as a resource	4.31	.674
Q4	We look for opportunities to learn more about knowledge for internal and external operations	4.27	.668
Q5	In their government work, our employees rely on experience, skills and knowledge	4.48	.671

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Q6	Our organization encourages and rewards the sharing of knowledge	4.18	.841
Q7	Our organization encourages engaging in dialogue or brainstorm session for new knowledge	4.31	.707
Q8	Workshops and training programs are thought sufficient in our organization for knowledge management	4.35	.699
Q9	Our organization thinks that the knowledge sharing results in increased proper practice and performance	4.42	.710
Q10	Protecting one's knowledge is considered to be a way of life in this organization	4.23	.699
Q11	Personally gained experience is considered as an important input for knowledge management in our organization	4.21	.670
Q12	Our organization is fair in knowledge-related performance measurement	4.24	.635
Q13	Explicit knowledge is seen as a significant aspect for financial knowledge in the organization	4.34	.563
Q14	The organization has better communicated relevant knowledge with employees for better knowledge management practice	4.25	.645
Q15	Organizational knowledge is expressed by employees such a way that the organization gets benefit from it	3.94	.904
Q16	Our organization gives priority to the understanding of successful and purposeful knowledge management practice that explains effective strategy	3.91	.819
Q17	Our organization thinks that appropriate knowledge management practice helps to explain the reasoning which enhances proper strategy for business performance	4.17	.809
Q18	Employees in our organization have gained a good extent of knowledge management structure that employs an expected organizational performance	3.95	.807
Q19	Our organization culture encourages teamwork among the employees	4.21	.826
Q20	Our organization culture improves involvement of workers in the workplace	4.33	.759
Q21	We have an open and trusting culture to increase the organizational performance	4.22	.729
Q22	In our organization, knowledge management structure is encouraged for expected knowledge management practice and organizational success	4.02	.866
Q23	Training and learning in regard to appropriate knowledge management strategy is adequate in the organization	4.17	.885
Q24	The knowledge management is communicated throughout the organization for performing suitable risk taking activities	4.29	1.061

Q25	We encourage employees to benchmark other organizations' best practices	4.46	.797
Q26	For our knowledge management process/activities, our organization does have specific goals and objectives	3.82	.648
Q27	Our organization provides sufficient managerial and operational efforts for appropriate strategy	3.83	.932
Q28	The environment of our organization has established a suitable process which supports controlling of management strategy	3.77	.896
Q29	In our organization, all relative documents are sent out to the respective people in a timely manner	4.10	.977
Q30	The organization controls its knowledge management, make ends meet, plan for the future and choose a suitable knowledge management practice	3.90	.912
Q31	Management control and checking records are appropriately exercised in our organization	3.67	.757
Q32	Managerial records are kept in proper manner in our organization	3.48	.932
Q33	We establish internal benchmark on coordination of strategy, budget, HR systems	3.59	.805
Q34	Our organization's knowledge management is based on management's established structure	3.54	.997
Q35	There is a written knowledge management report prepared by the top management which is raised in each management meeting	3.95	.734
Q36	Our organization's sales turnover has increased	3.94	.845
Q37	Our organization's market share has increased	4.03	.902
Q38	The number of employees has increased in our organization	3.75	.792
Q39	There is an improvement in preparing for the future financial growth	3.68	.807
Q40	There is an improvement in overall business circumstance of our organization	3.68	.822

The study aimed to identify the construct validity of Knowledge Management Structure (KMS), Knowledge Management Practice (KMP), Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST) and Organizational Performance on the basis of data collected from 331 respondents (n = 331) who were the executives, non-executive and the employees of various Government Entities (GE) in Abu Dhabi. The dimensionality of the Knowledge Management Structure (KMS), Knowledge Management Practice (KMP), Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST) and Organizational Performance (OP) were sought through a principal component analysis (PCA) after which a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted to confirm the dimensionality obtained through PCA.

The PCA was to explore the underlying dimensions of Knowledge Management Structure (KMS), Knowledge Management Practice (KMP), Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST) and Organizational Performance within the Abu Dhabi Government Entities (GE) context. First, the statistical assumptions of PCA were tested. The exercise revealed that a substantial number of variables were correlated ($r \geq .30$). In addition, the two measures for inter-correlations among variables supported the use of PCA (Hair et al., 2010; Kline, 2011; Kothari, 2004; Neuman, 2007). Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity was statistically significant [4190.487, $p = .000$], while the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of the sampling adequacy (MSA) was .857, indicating that the inter-correlations were sufficient for PCA (Pallant, 2007) (Table 2).

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett’s Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.857
Approx. Chi-Square	4190.487
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	
df	406
Sig.	.000

PCA with Varimax rotation was performed on the data collected. Four latent factors were extracted with eigenvalues greater than one, explaining 55.70% of total variance (Table 3). Thus, the results show that four latent factors were successfully extracted on 29 items. Table 3 shows that factor loadings are between .531 and .784. Following the guideline provided by the scholars (Byrne, 2010; Hair et al., 2010, Kline, 2011; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994), all four factors were renamed as Knowledge Management Structure (KMS), Knowledge Management Practice (KMP), Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST) and Organizational Performance, respectively.

Table 3: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	7.818	26.960	26.960	7.818	26.960	26.960	5.845	20.156	20.156
2	3.766	12.987	39.946	3.766	12.987	39.946	3.604	12.427	32.583
3	2.490	8.587	48.533	2.490	8.587	48.533	3.476	11.987	44.571
4	2.078	7.167	55.700	2.078	7.167	55.700	3.227	11.129	55.700
5	.942	3.249	58.948						
6	.914	3.151	62.099						

7	.880	3.034	65.133
8	.845	2.914	68.047
9	.785	2.708	70.755
10	.720	2.484	73.239
11	.702	2.421	75.660
12	.646	2.229	77.889
13	.620	2.140	80.029
14	.548	1.888	81.917
15	.518	1.785	83.702
16	.499	1.720	85.423
17	.464	1.599	87.022
18	.460	1.588	88.610
19	.431	1.485	90.094
20	.405	1.397	91.492
21	.364	1.256	92.748
22	.360	1.241	93.989
23	.342	1.179	95.168
24	.279	.964	96.132
25	.270	.929	97.061
26	.254	.874	97.936
27	.227	.782	98.718
28	.205	.709	99.427
29	.166	.573	100.000

Table 4: Loadings Four Rotated Factors

Code	Item	Knowledge Management Structure (KMS)	Knowledge Management Practice (KMP)	Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST)	Organizational Performance (OP)
Q1	Our employees obtain a good extent of new knowledge from internal and external sources	.697			
Q2	Our employees gain new knowledge from business partners and rivals	.728			
Q3	Our organization recognizes knowledge creation as a resource	.752			

Code	Item	Knowledge Management Structure (KMS)	Knowledge Management Practice (KMP)	Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST)	Organizational Performance (OP)
Q4	We look for opportunities to learn more about knowledge for internal and external operations	.730			
Q5	In their government work, our employees rely on experience, skills and knowledge	.704			
Q6	Our organization encourages and rewards the sharing of knowledge	.773			
Q7	Our organization encourages engaging in dialogue or brainstorm session for new knowledge	.743			
Q8	Workshops and training programs are thought sufficient in our organization for knowledge management	.707			
Q9	Our organization thinks that the knowledge sharing results in increased proper practice and performance		.767		
Q10	Protecting one's knowledge is considered to be a way of life in this organization		.763		
Q11	Personally gained experience is considered as an important input for knowledge management in our organization		.784		
Q12	Our organization is fair in knowledge-related performance measurement		.756		
Q13	Explicit knowledge is seen as a significant aspect for financial knowledge in the organization		.650		
Q14	The organization has better communicated relevant knowledge with employees for better knowledge management practice			.707	
Q15	Organizational knowledge is expressed by employees such a way that the organization gets benefit from it			.757	
Q16	Our organization gives priority to the understanding of successful and purposeful knowledge management practice that explains effective strategy			.747	
Q17	Our organization thinks that appropriate knowledge management practice helps to explain the reasoning which enhances proper strategy for business performance			.616	

Code	Item	Knowledge Management Structure (KMS)	Knowledge Management Practice (KMP)	Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST)	Organizational Performance (OP)
Q18	Employees in our organization have gained a good extent of knowledge management structure that employs an expected organizational performance			.596	
Q19	Our organization culture encourages teamwork among the employees			.581	
Q20	Our organization culture improves involvement of workers in the workplace			.609	
Q21	We have an open and trusting culture to increase the organizational performance				.733
Q22	In our organization, knowledge management structure is encouraged for expected knowledge management practice and organizational success				.752
Q23	Training and learning in regard to appropriate knowledge management strategy is adequate in the organization				.736
Q24	The knowledge management is communicated throughout the organization for performing suitable risk taking activities				.701
Q25	We encourage employees to benchmark other organizations' best practices				.615
Q26	For our knowledge management process/activities, our organization does have specific goals and objectives				.680

The internal consistency of all the factors were obtained by computing the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient on the four extracted factors was retained by PCA. In view of the guidelines by researchers (Cronbach, 1951; Sekaran & Bougie, 2010), Cronbach's Alpha was employed to estimate the reliability of the extracted factors as presented in Table 5. All four factors [Knowledge Management Structure (KMS), Knowledge Management Practice (KMP), Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST) and Organizational Performance (OP)] had good reliability indices of .856, .799, .786 and .833, respectively.

Table 5: Reliability Statistics

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Knowledge Management Structure (KMS)	.856	7
Knowledge Management Practice (KMP)	.799	5
Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST)	.786	7
Organizational Performance (OP)	.833	6
Overall	.897	29

The following section presents the results of EFA to support the construct validity of Knowledge Management Structure (KMS), Knowledge Management Practice (KMP), Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST) and Organizational Performance (OP). The factors derived from the results of the PCA contain the four variables loaded on 26 indicators. The first variable is Knowledge Management Structure (KMS), second variable is Knowledge Management Practice (KMP), third variable is Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST) and the variable is Organizational Performance (OP).

The interrelationships among the 26 measures of Knowledge Management Structure (KMS), Knowledge Management Practice (KMP), Knowledge Management Strategy (KMST) and Organizational Performance were checked at the estimates section of the AMOS (version 21.0) text output and it showed that the indices were statistically significant. For normality, the use of AMOS showed through the indices of skewness and kurtosis that there was no serious violation of the assumption of normality as all values of skewness were negative and less than 3 (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988; Barrett, 2007; Bollen, 1989; Byrne, 2010; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007) (Table 6). This is the justification for the researcher's adoption of CFA for further data analysis.

Table 6: Assessment of Normality

Code	Item	Skew	Kurtosis
Q1	Our employees obtain a good extent of new knowledge from internal and external sources	-.285	-.087
Q2	Our employees gain new knowledge from business partners and rivals	-.371	.111
Q3	Our organization recognizes knowledge creation as a resource	-.289	.488
Q4	We look for opportunities to learn more about knowledge for internal and external operations	-.262	.242
Q5	In their government work, our employees rely on experience, skills and knowledge	-.338	.726
Q6	Our organization encourages and rewards the sharing of knowledge	-.143	-.064
Q7	Our organization encourages engaging in dialogue or brainstorm session for new knowledge	-.321	-.188

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Code	Item	Skew	Kurtosis
Q8	Workshops and training programs are thought sufficient in our organization for knowledge management	-.053	-.444
Q9	Our organization thinks that the knowledge sharing results in increased proper practice and performance	-.653	.309
Q10	Protecting one's knowledge is considered to be a way of life in this organization	-.555	.512
Q11	Personally gained experience is considered as an important input for knowledge management in our organization	-.823	.959
Q12	Our organization is fair in knowledge-related performance measurement	-.277	-.602
Q13	Explicit knowledge is seen as a significant aspect for financial knowledge in the organization	-.586	-.519
Q14	The organization has better communicated relevant knowledge with employees for better knowledge management practice	-.479	.003
Q15	Organizational knowledge is expressed by employees such a way that the organization gets benefit from it	-.574	-.240
Q16	Our organization gives priority to the understanding of successful and purposeful knowledge management practice that explains effective strategy	-.837	.968
Q17	Our organization thinks that appropriate knowledge management practice helps to explain the reasoning which enhances proper strategy for business performance	-.743	.401
Q18	Employees in our organization have gained a good extent of knowledge management structure that employs an expected organizational performance	-.836	.262
Q19	Our organization culture encourages teamwork among the employees	-.726	.858
Q20	Our organization culture improves involvement of workers in the workplace	-.513	-.167
Q21	We have an open and trusting culture to increase the organizational performance	-.912	1.246
Q22	In our organization, knowledge management structure is encouraged for expected knowledge management practice and organizational success	-.612	-.789
Q23	Training and learning in regard to appropriate knowledge management strategy is adequate in the organization	-.579	.043
Q24	The knowledge management is communicated throughout the organization for performing suitable risk taking activities	-.397	-.248
Q25	We encourage employees to benchmark other organizations' best practices	-.328	-.266
Q26	For our knowledge management process/activities, our organization does have specific goals and objectives	-.266	-.710
Multivariate			125.175

5. Conclusion and Implication

This research has contributed to the existing knowledge by proposing an empirically tested/validated model which could be used to predict a material portion of the variables that contributes to the eventual success of the government entities. The proposed model elaborates as to how independent variables, knowledge management structure and knowledge management practice are influencing the dependent variable together with the level of influence each of the independent variables exert on the success of government entities performance. Among notable contribution to the theory are;

1. Building a model to test contribution of knowledge management structure and knowledge management practice to government entities performance
2. Validating the model through empirical testing
3. Advancement of knowledge via bridging knowledge gap of respective contribution by variables and their significance
4. New knowledge being imparted and areas for future research identified as model validation covered the entire country of Abu Dhabi due to representativeness of the sample.
5. Extension of existing theory in areas of knowledge management structure and knowledge management practice in the presence of each other variable than in isolation
6. Future research opportunities created to test the model in other countries as cultural impact of mediating impact of knowledge management strategy on the relationship between knowledge management structure and government entities performance has played a role.

Literature revealed that the available limited research lacks validation through empirical research whereas this research has bridged the said research gap through comprehensive empirical testing and confirming the hypothesis. Constructs for the independent variables were established and yet again empirically tested for their relevance, validity and contribution. This has brought about new knowledge to the researchers which may be tested or contested due to country conditions being different to that of Abu Dhabi or laps of time has altered the findings as of a future date. Future researchers could identify emerging variables that may alter the significance of variables tested which may lead to completely new discoveries as to what contributes to the success of government entities.

Previous researches have investigated the independent variable's contribution in isolation towards government entities performance however the collective contribution

by the variables were not studied. Similarly, previous models lack any identified effect due to mediating variables. This research has bridged above research gaps by expanding on former researchers recommendation and has inquired in to the collective impact of the independent variables while intervened by knowledge management strategy.

Knowledge management structure and knowledge management structure is an emerging topic among the government entities in Abu Dhabi in order to improve business performance. Effective knowledge management structure allowed the government entities to obtain a better understanding about the dynamic business surrounding and rapidly changing landscape relating to the stakeholder expectations. This research will contributes to the existing knowledge database significantly, as prior researches were focusing on business other than the government entities and countries other than in Abu Dhabi. Also, based on the literature review, this appears to be the first time this model is empirically tested which incorporated the knowledge management strategy as the mediating variables thus enhancing the knowledge on this particular field of study. Apart from that, the knowledge gained from this study may be applied to other business segments in Abu Dhabi such as micro business and larger business on government entities.

The findings of the research and literature review indicated the research gap that the inadequacy of available literature to elaborate in Abu Dhabi context as to whether knowledge management structure and knowledge management practice makes an impact on the government entities' performance. Although limited empirical research were found in other countries relating to knowledge management structure and knowledge management practice and its impact on business performance, those research were conducted in the respective countries during the earlier years and hence the evolution of subject matter to today's context was lacking. In many of the instances the business performance of the larger organizations were researched to understand the impact of knowledge management structure and knowledge management practice. This research is the first of its kind in Abu Dhabi which proposes a model for the government entities and empirically tested the model via a study covering all the provinces in Abu Dhabi.

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